

BUCKLING ANALYSIS OF VARIABLE ANGLE TOW, VARIABLE THICKNESS PANELS WITH TRANSVERSE SHEAR EFFECTS

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1 Introduction

The idea of tailoring the structural performance of composite laminates by spatially varying the point-wise fibre orientations over the planform has been explored since the early 1990's. For example, the work by Hyer & Lee [1] and Hyer & Charette [2] showed that such variable angle tow (VAT) laminates can improve the stress concentration around holes by arranging the fibres in the direction of load paths. In recent years the use of fibre re-reinforced composites in primary aircraft structures has led to increased interest in VAT technology. Numerous works have shown that tailoring the in-plane stiffness of a plate allows pre-buckling stresses to be re-distributed to supported regions and thereby improve the buckling behaviour [3–7]. In this manner VAT technology has been shown to improve the buckling performance of a composite fuselage window section by 12% compared to an equivalent straight-fibre laminate [8] and alleviate the pressure pillowing of fuselage sections [9]. Recent results by Wu et al. [10] show that VAT plates with linear fibre variations can be designed to exhibit smaller stiffness reductions in the post-buckling regime than their straight-fibre counterparts. What is more, the optimum fibre orientations for increasing the buckling load are similar to those for minimising the transverse displacement in the post-buckling regime [11].

Currently the major technology for manufacturing VAT laminates is the automated fibre placement (AFP) technique developed in the 1980's. AFP uses a robotic fibre placement head that deposits multiple pre-impregnated tows of "slit-tape" allowing cutting, clamping and restarting of every single tow. While the robotic head follows a specific fibre path, tows are heated shortly before deposition and then compacted onto the substrate using a special roller. Due to the high fidelity of current robot technology AFP machines can provide high productivity and handle complex geometries [12]. However, AFP steers tows by bending the fibres causing local fibre buckling on the inside radii of the curved tow, consequently limiting the steering radius of curvature [13]. Furthermore, if individual tows are placed next to each other by shifting the reference path along a specific direction, tow gaps and overlaps are in-

evitably required to cover the whole surface. To overcome the drawbacks of AFP the continuous tow shearing technique (CTS) was developed which uses shear deformation to steer fibres at the point of application [14]. This technique not only allows much tighter radii of curvature but tow gaps and overlaps are also avoided by tessalating tows on the substrate [14]. One of the drawbacks of CTS is that in order to maintain the volume fraction of fibre the thickness of a tow inherently increases as it is sheared. The relation between unshered tow thickness t_0 and sheared tow thickness t_θ is,

$$t_\theta = \frac{t_0}{\cos \theta} \quad (1)$$

where θ is the shearing angle of the tow. Consequently the thickness of a ply may locally increase by a factor of 4 if the fibre tow is sheared through an angle of 75°, the effects of which are currently unaccounted for in buckling optimisation studies. Furthermore, since composite laminates are more affected by transverse shear effects than isotropic materials these local areas of increased thickness make predictions of the buckling behaviour using Classical Laminate Analysis (CLA) [15] overly conservative [16,17]. Buckling optimisation algorithms using the Finite Element method (FEM) can become computationally expensive, and do not readily shed physical insight into the fundamental mechanisms in which thickness variations may enhance the buckling behaviour. For this reason a reduced 2D equivalent single-layer formulation for the flexural behaviour of VAT plate incorporating transverse shear effects was developed [18]. Indeed, it was shown that CLA predictions result in discrepancies of over 15% for thickness to length ratios of 1:20. Thus, considering the extent of thickness variation possible using CTS, transverse shear effects need to be incorporated if the spatial fibre distribution is to be optimised accurately for buckling and post-buckling behaviour.

In this work, the buckling behaviour of VAT plates with linear fibre variations manufactured using the CTS technique is analysed using the aforementioned 2D equivalent single-layer formulation. Section 2 outlines the theoretical background of the model. In Section 4, the governing equations are solved in the strong form for various load and boundary conditions and validated by 2D FEM and 3D

FEM techniques. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

2 Theory

2.1 Modelling of variable thickness cross-section

Linear fibre variations can conveniently be defined by the notation $\theta = \phi < T_0 | T_1 >$, where ϕ denotes the rotation of the fibre path with respect to the x -axis, while T_0 and T_1 are the fibre angles at the ply centre and a characteristic length d from the centre respectively [3]. To fill the planform the fibre trajectories are then shifted perpendicular to the steering direction ϕ . A $90 < 0 | 70 >$ VAT layer is drawn schematically in Figure 1.

Figure 1: CTS manufactured $90 < 0 | 70 >$ layer with reference path shifted in the x -direction, showing fibre orientations and thickness variations

The thickness variation produced by CTS means that the VAT laminate now resembles a flat plate on one side and a cylindrical shell on the other. If this 3D structure is compressed onto an equivalent single-layer coincident with the mid-plane at each point, the reference layer will resemble a thin cylindrical shell (Curve 1 in Fig. 1). In the present theory the hypothesis is made that the VAT laminate continues to behave as a flat plate with the reference surface coincident with the mid-plane of the nominal (unsheared)

laminate thickness (Curve 2 in Fig. 1). Thus, the equivalent single-layer is assumed to behave as a non-symmetric laminate in areas of increased thickness. As a first approximation we do not attempt to solve the coupled stretching-bending problem but use the more straightforward, albeit less accurate technique, of substituting the reduced stiffness matrices $\mathbf{A}^* = \mathbf{A} - \mathbf{B}^{-1}\mathbf{D}\mathbf{B}$ and $\mathbf{D}^* = \mathbf{A} - \mathbf{B}^{-1}\mathbf{D}\mathbf{B}$ [19], and reduced flexibility $\mathbf{d}^* = \mathbf{D}^{*-1}$ in the equations for the symmetric equations derived in the following sections.

2.2 Variational formulation including transverse shear stress

In the present theory, the constitutive equations between in-plane forces, bending moments, in-plane strains and curvatures that underpin CLA are originally retained. Furthermore, we assume linear variations of in-plane stresses through the laminate thickness. Writing the equations for a symmetric laminate in inversed notation the stresses at a given location z are given by,

$$\vec{\sigma}_k = \bar{\mathbf{Q}}_k \left[\mathbf{a}\vec{\mathbf{N}} + z\mathbf{d}\vec{\mathbf{M}} \right] \quad (2)$$

$$(3)$$

where \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{d} are the in-plane and bending flexibilities respectively. The transverse shear stresses are derived by integrating the in-plane stresses Eq. (2) in Cauchy's equilibrium equations in the thickness z -direction. The constants of integration are eliminated by enforcing boundary conditions of shear stress continuity at each ply interface. As a result, the effect of the thickness is condensed onto an equivalent single-layer coincident with the mid-plane. Thus for a symmetric laminate the transverse shear stress for a particular layer k is given by [20],

$$\vec{\tau}_k = -\mathbf{C} \left[\bar{\mathbf{A}}_k(x, y, z) \left(\mathbf{a}\vec{\mathbf{N}} \right) + \bar{\mathbf{B}}_k(x, y, z) \left(\mathbf{d}\vec{\mathbf{M}} \right) \right] \quad (4)$$

where

$$\bar{\mathbf{A}}_k(x, y, z) = \bar{\mathbf{Q}}_k (z - z_{k-1}) + \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \bar{\mathbf{Q}}_j (z_j - z_{j-1}) \quad (5)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{B}}_k(x, y, z) = \frac{1}{2} \bar{\mathbf{Q}}_k (z^2 - z_{k-1}^2) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \bar{\mathbf{Q}}_j (z_j^2 - z_{j-1}^2) \quad (6)$$

$$\text{and } \mathbf{C} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \\ 0 & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

By observing Eqs. (5) and (6) it can be seen that $\bar{\mathbf{A}}_k$ and $\bar{\mathbf{B}}_k$ respectively define the partial in-plane stiffness and partial coupling stiffness terms up to the ply k under consideration. Under pure transverse loading the in-plane load resultants $\vec{\mathbf{N}}$ vanish and Eq. (4) reduces to,

$$\vec{\tau}_k = -\mathbf{C}\bar{\mathbf{B}}_k\mathbf{d}\vec{\mathbf{M}} \quad (8)$$

Equilibrium equations for a VAT panel in pure bending including the effects of transverse shear deformation are derived using the Hellinger-Reissner mixed variational principle. By definition the total potential energy of the 3D system is given by,

$$\Pi = \frac{1}{2} \int \int \int (\bar{\sigma}^T \bar{\epsilon} + \bar{\tau}^T \bar{\gamma} + \sigma_z \epsilon_z) dx dy dz - \int \int (\sigma_n u_n + \tau_{ns} u_s + \tau_{nz} w) ds dz \quad (9)$$

The variation of the functional Π must vanish in such a manner that transverse equilibrium is satisfied. The shear stress resultants V_x and V_y are related to the transverse load intensity p by the following equilibrium equation,

$$\frac{\partial V_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial V_y}{\partial y} + p = 0 \quad (10)$$

Following Reissner's mixed variational principle [21] this is achieved by adding Eq. (10) to the variation of the functional Π as a constraint using a Lagrange multiplier $\lambda(x, y)$. Thus,

$$\delta \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{l_x} \int_0^{l_y} \int_{z_0}^{z_n} (\bar{\sigma}^T \bar{\mathbf{Q}}_k^{-1} \bar{\sigma} + \bar{\tau}^T \bar{\mathbf{G}}_k^{-1} \bar{\tau}) dz dy dx - \int_{z_0}^{z_n} \oint_{\Gamma} (\sigma_n u_n + \tau_{ns} u_s + \tau_{nz} w) ds dz + \int_0^{l_x} \int_0^{l_y} \lambda \left(\frac{\partial V_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial V_y}{\partial y} + p \right) dy dx \right\} = 0 \quad (11)$$

2.3 Governing equations for bending

After substituting Eq. (2) into Eq. (11) the variations with respect to the unknown fields $\bar{\mathbf{M}}$ and Lagrange multiplier $\lambda(x, y)$ are performed using the calculus of variations. The derivations are presented in detail in [18]. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \delta \Pi = & \int_0^{l_x} \int_0^{l_y} \left[\mathbf{d}\bar{\mathbf{M}}(\delta\bar{\mathbf{M}}) + \left(\bar{\alpha}\mathbf{M} + \bar{\alpha}^x \frac{\partial \mathbf{M}}{\partial x} + \bar{\alpha}^y \frac{\partial \mathbf{M}}{\partial y} + \bar{\alpha}^{xx} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{M}}{\partial x^2} + \bar{\alpha}^{yy} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{M}}{\partial y^2} + \bar{\alpha}^{xy} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{M}}{\partial x \partial y} \right) \delta \mathbf{M} + \right. \\ & \left. \frac{\partial^2 \lambda}{\partial x^2} (\delta M_x) + 2 \frac{\partial^2 \lambda}{\partial x \partial y} (\delta M_{xy}) + \frac{\partial^2 \lambda}{\partial y^2} (\delta M_y) \right. \\ & \left. \left(\frac{\partial^2 M_x}{\partial x^2} + 2 \frac{\partial^2 M_{xy}}{\partial x \partial y} + \frac{\partial^2 M_y}{\partial y^2} + p \right) (\delta \lambda) \right] dy dx + \\ & \oint_{\Gamma} \left[\left(\bar{\beta}\mathbf{M} + \bar{\beta}^x \frac{\partial \mathbf{M}}{\partial x} + \bar{\beta}^y \frac{\partial \mathbf{M}}{\partial y} \right) \delta \mathbf{M} + (\lambda - \bar{w}) \delta V_n \right. \\ & \left. - n_x \left(\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x} + \bar{u}'_x \right) \delta M_x - \left\{ n_y \left(\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x} + \bar{u}'_x \right) + \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. n_x \left(\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial y} + \bar{u}'_y \right) \right\} \delta M_{xy} - n_y \left(\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial y} + \bar{u}'_y \right) \delta M_y \right] ds \quad (12) \end{aligned}$$

where n_x and n_y are the directional cosines of the tangent vector to the boundary curve Γ , and $\bar{\alpha}$ and $\bar{\beta}$ terms are 3×3

matrices that represent the shear coefficients of the present theory. To guarantee that $\delta \Pi = 0$ the coefficients of the variations of $\bar{\mathbf{M}}$, V_n and λ must equate to zero in both the double and the line integrals. In this manner, the governing field equations are derived from the double integrals and the pertinent boundary conditions from the line integrals,

$$\begin{aligned} \delta M_x : & (d_{11} + \alpha_{11}) M_x + (d_{12} + \alpha_{12}) M_y + (d_{16} + \alpha_{13}) M_{xy} \\ & + \alpha_{11}^x \frac{\partial M_x}{\partial x} + \alpha_{12}^x \frac{\partial M_y}{\partial x} + \alpha_{13}^x \frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial x} + \alpha_{11}^y \frac{\partial M_x}{\partial y} + \alpha_{12}^y \frac{\partial M_y}{\partial y} \\ & + \alpha_{13}^y \frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial y} + \alpha_{11}^{xx} \frac{\partial^2 M_x}{\partial x^2} + \alpha_{12}^{xx} \frac{\partial^2 M_y}{\partial x^2} + \alpha_{13}^{xx} \frac{\partial^2 M_{xy}}{\partial x^2} \\ & + \alpha_{11}^{yy} \frac{\partial^2 M_x}{\partial y^2} + \alpha_{12}^{yy} \frac{\partial^2 M_y}{\partial y^2} + \alpha_{13}^{yy} \frac{\partial^2 M_{xy}}{\partial y^2} + \alpha_{11}^{xy} \frac{\partial^2 M_x}{\partial x \partial y} \\ & + \alpha_{12}^{xy} \frac{\partial^2 M_y}{\partial x \partial y} + \alpha_{13}^{xy} \frac{\partial^2 M_{xy}}{\partial x \partial y} = - \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \quad (13a) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \delta M_y : & (d_{12} + \alpha_{21}) M_x + (d_{22} + \alpha_{22}) M_y + (d_{26} + \alpha_{23}) M_{xy} \\ & + \alpha_{21}^x \frac{\partial M_x}{\partial x} + \alpha_{22}^x \frac{\partial M_y}{\partial x} + \alpha_{23}^x \frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial x} + \alpha_{21}^y \frac{\partial M_x}{\partial y} + \alpha_{22}^y \frac{\partial M_y}{\partial y} \\ & + \alpha_{23}^y \frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial y} + \alpha_{21}^{xx} \frac{\partial^2 M_x}{\partial x^2} + \alpha_{22}^{xx} \frac{\partial^2 M_y}{\partial x^2} + \alpha_{23}^{xx} \frac{\partial^2 M_{xy}}{\partial x^2} \\ & + \alpha_{21}^{yy} \frac{\partial^2 M_x}{\partial y^2} + \alpha_{22}^{yy} \frac{\partial^2 M_y}{\partial y^2} + \alpha_{23}^{yy} \frac{\partial^2 M_{xy}}{\partial y^2} + \alpha_{21}^{xy} \frac{\partial^2 M_x}{\partial x \partial y} \\ & + \alpha_{22}^{xy} \frac{\partial^2 M_y}{\partial x \partial y} + \alpha_{23}^{xy} \frac{\partial^2 M_{xy}}{\partial x \partial y} = - \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \quad (13b) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \delta M_{xy} : & (d_{16} + \alpha_{31}) M_x + (d_{26} + \alpha_{32}) M_y + (d_{66} + \alpha_{33}) M_{xy} \\ & + \alpha_{31}^x \frac{\partial M_x}{\partial x} + \alpha_{32}^x \frac{\partial M_y}{\partial x} + \alpha_{33}^x \frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial x} + \alpha_{31}^y \frac{\partial M_x}{\partial y} + \alpha_{32}^y \frac{\partial M_y}{\partial y} \\ & + \alpha_{33}^y \frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial y} + \alpha_{31}^{xx} \frac{\partial^2 M_x}{\partial x^2} + \alpha_{32}^{xx} \frac{\partial^2 M_y}{\partial x^2} + \alpha_{33}^{xx} \frac{\partial^2 M_{xy}}{\partial x^2} \\ & + \alpha_{31}^{yy} \frac{\partial^2 M_x}{\partial y^2} + \alpha_{32}^{yy} \frac{\partial^2 M_y}{\partial y^2} + \alpha_{33}^{yy} \frac{\partial^2 M_{xy}}{\partial y^2} + \alpha_{31}^{xy} \frac{\partial^2 M_x}{\partial x \partial y} \\ & + \alpha_{32}^{xy} \frac{\partial^2 M_y}{\partial x \partial y} + \alpha_{33}^{xy} \frac{\partial^2 M_{xy}}{\partial x \partial y} = -2 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \quad (13c) \end{aligned}$$

$$\delta \lambda : \frac{\partial^2 M_x}{\partial x^2} + 2 \frac{\partial^2 M_{xy}}{\partial x \partial y} + \frac{\partial^2 M_y}{\partial y^2} = -p \quad (13d)$$

Thus, the flexural behaviour of the plate for a specific transverse loading p is described by four unknown fields M_x , M_y , M_{xy} and w that are related by the four differential equations (13). Eqs. (13a) - (13c) include differential terms of M_x , M_y and M_{xy} multiplied by various $\bar{\alpha}$ coefficients that can be interpreted as transverse shear flexibilities. The displacement boundary conditions are derived from the coefficients in the line integral,

$$\begin{aligned} \delta M_x : & \beta_{11} M_x + \beta_{12} M_y + \beta_{13} M_{xy} + \beta_{11}^x \frac{\partial M_x}{\partial x} + \beta_{12}^x \frac{\partial M_y}{\partial x} + \\ & \beta_{13}^x \frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial x} + \beta_{11}^y \frac{\partial M_x}{\partial y} + \beta_{12}^y \frac{\partial M_y}{\partial y} + \beta_{13}^y \frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial y} - n_x \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \\ & = n_x \bar{u}'_x \quad (14a) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \delta M_y : & \beta_{21} M_x + \beta_{22} M_y + \beta_{23} M_{xy} + \beta_{21}^x \frac{\partial M_x}{\partial x} + \beta_{22}^x \frac{\partial M_y}{\partial x} + \\ & \beta_{23}^x \frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial x} + \beta_{21}^y \frac{\partial M_x}{\partial y} + \beta_{22}^y \frac{\partial M_y}{\partial y} + \beta_{23}^y \frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial y} - n_y \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \\ & = n_y \bar{u}'_y \end{aligned} \quad (14b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \delta M_{xy} : & \beta_{31} M_x + \beta_{32} M_y + \beta_{33} M_{xy} + \beta_{31}^x \frac{\partial M_x}{\partial x} + \beta_{32}^x \frac{\partial M_y}{\partial x} + \\ & \beta_{33}^x \frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial x} + \beta_{31}^y \frac{\partial M_x}{\partial y} + \beta_{32}^y \frac{\partial M_y}{\partial y} + \beta_{33}^y \frac{\partial M_{xy}}{\partial y} - n_x \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} - \\ & n_y \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} = n_x \bar{u}'_x + n_y \bar{u}'_y \end{aligned} \quad (14c)$$

$$\delta V_n : \lambda = \bar{w} = w \quad (14d)$$

which have to be applied if the force boundary conditions $M_x = \bar{M}_x$, $M_y = \bar{M}_y$, $M_{xy} = \bar{M}_{xy}$ or $V_n = \bar{V}_n$ are not specified.

3 Solving the buckling problem

Since the in-plane stiffness matrix \mathbf{A} varies spatially from point to point, even constant applied edge loads or displacements will result in non-uniform in-plane stress distributions $\bar{\sigma}_x(x,y)$, $\bar{\sigma}_y(x,y)$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{xy}(x,y)$ [4]. It is important to accurately determine the in-plane stress distribution in order to accurately solve the linear buckling eigenvalue problem. By observation of Cauchy's in-plane equilibrium equations,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \bar{\sigma}_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{xy}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{xz}}{\partial z} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \bar{\sigma}_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \bar{\sigma}_{yz}}{\partial z} &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

the varying stress distributions $\bar{\sigma}_x(x,y)$, $\bar{\sigma}_y(x,y)$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{xy}(x,y)$ for a VAT plate under pure in-plane loading may require transverse shear stresses to satisfy equilibrium. However, in the present work the effect of transverse shear stresses on the pre-buckling problem is assumed to be negligible. Thus substituting the equations for the in-plane load resultants \bar{N} from CLA, where u and v are the mid-plane deformations in the defined x - and y - directions respectively,

$$N_x = A_{11} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + A_{12} \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + A_{16} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) \quad (15a)$$

$$N_y = A_{12} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + A_{22} \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + A_{26} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) \quad (15b)$$

$$N_{xy} = A_{16} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + A_{26} \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + A_{66} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) \quad (15c)$$

into the in-plane equilibrium equations written in terms of the stress resultants,

$$\frac{\partial N_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial N_{xy}}{\partial y} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial N_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial N_y}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (16a-b)$$

we get,

$$\begin{aligned} A_{11} u_{,xx} + 2A_{16} u_{,xy} + A_{66} u_{,yy} + A_{16} v_{,xx} + (A_{12} + A_{66}) v_{,xy} + \\ A_{26} v_{,yy} + (A_{11,x} + A_{16,y}) u_{,x} + (A_{16,x} + A_{66,y}) u_{,y} + \\ (A_{16,x} + A_{66,y}) v_{,x} + (A_{12,x} + A_{26,y}) v_{,y} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (17a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} A_{16} u_{,xx} + (A_{12} + A_{66}) u_{,xy} + A_{26} u_{,yy} + A_{66} v_{,xx} + 2A_{26} v_{,xy} + \\ A_{22} v_{,yy} + (A_{16,x} + A_{12,y}) u_{,x} + (A_{66,x} + A_{26,y}) u_{,y} + \\ (A_{66,x} + A_{26,y}) v_{,x} + (A_{26,x} + A_{22,y}) v_{,y} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (17b)$$

which can be solved for u and v by prescribing the boundary conditions $u = \bar{u}$ or $N_{xy} = \bar{N}_{xy}$ on x , $u = \bar{u}$ or $N_x = \bar{N}_x$ on y , $v = \bar{v}$ or $N_y = \bar{N}_y$ on x , and $v = \bar{v}$ or $N_{xy} = \bar{N}_{xy}$ on y . Once u and v are known under the prescribed boundary conditions the in-plane stress resultants are found using Eq. (15). Thus, by replacing the transverse pressure p in Eq. (13d) by the out-of-plane components of the in-plane stress resultants,

$$\frac{\partial^2 M_x}{\partial x^2} + 2 \frac{\partial^2 M_{xy}}{\partial x \partial y} + \frac{\partial^2 M_y}{\partial y^2} = -N_x \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} - 2N_{xy} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} - N_y \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2}$$

the buckling problem of Eqs. (13) can be solved. Recently, the Differential Quadrature Method (DQM) has been shown to be a fast, accurate and computationally efficient technique for solving the variable coefficient, higher order differential equations [7, 18]. Differential quadrature is a numerical discretization technique that approximates the partial derivatives of a functional field with respect to a specific spatial variable using a linear weighted sum of all the functional values in the domain. For example, the n^{th} partial derivative at the i^{th} discretization point is,

$$\frac{\partial^n f(x_i)}{\partial x^n} = A_{ij}^{(n)} f(x_j) \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N$$

where x_i is the set of discretization points in the x -direction, typically defined by the non-uniform Gauss-Labotto-Chebyshev distribution,

$$x_i = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 - \cos \left(\frac{i-1}{N-1} \pi \right) \right], \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (18)$$

A_{ij}^n are the weighting coefficients of the n^{th} derivative and repeated index j means summation from 1 to N . The weighting coefficients are determined by approximating $f(x)$ using test functions. In this work, Lagrange polynomials defined by Quan & Chang [22] are used,

$$g_k(x) = \frac{M(x)}{(x-x_k)M^{(1)}(x_k)}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, N$$

where $M(x) = \prod_{j=1}^N (x-x_j)$, $M^{(1)}(x_i) = \prod_{k=1, k \neq i}^N (x_i-x_k)$

$$\Rightarrow A_{ij}^{(1)} = \frac{1}{x_j - x_i} \prod_{k=1, k \neq i, j}^N \frac{x_i - x_k}{x_j - x_k}, \quad \text{for } i \neq j$$

$$\text{and } A_{ii}^{(1)} = \sum_{k=1, k \neq i}^N \frac{1}{x_i - x_k} \quad (19)$$

The higher order weighting coefficients are then obtained by direct matrix multiplication: $[A^{(m)}] = [A^{(1)}][A^{(m-1)}]$, $m = 2, 3, \dots, N - 1$ [23]. Thus, a differential equation is reduced to a system of algebraic equations and the unknown functional values at each grid point are found by solving the system of equations with the appropriate boundary conditions. Thus the in-plane problem Eqs. (17) is re-written as,

$$\begin{bmatrix} K_{1u} & K_{1v} \\ K_{2u} & K_{2v} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \Rightarrow \mathbf{K}\vec{U} = 0 \quad (20)$$

and once u and v are known across the plate, the general eigenvalue problem defined by Eqs. (13) is solved,

$$\left\{ \begin{bmatrix} K_{11} & K_{12} & K_{13} & K_{14} \\ K_{21} & K_{22} & K_{23} & K_{24} \\ K_{31} & K_{32} & K_{33} & K_{34} \\ K_{41} & K_{42} & K_{43} & K_{44} \end{bmatrix} - \lambda \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & N \end{bmatrix} \right\} \begin{pmatrix} M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \\ w \end{pmatrix} = (\mathbf{K} - \lambda\mathbf{N})\vec{X} = \mathbf{0} \quad (21)$$

where λ is the buckling eigenvalue, \mathbf{K} is a matrix of DQ coefficients, bending flexibilities and shear coefficients, \vec{X} the vector of unknown functional values at the grid points, and \mathbf{N} a matrix of DQ coefficients and pre-buckling in-plane stress resultants. The boundary equations can be discretised in a similar fashion and then applied using Shu & Du's general approach [24]. Here the discretised mesh is separated into grid point values \vec{X}_b on the boundary and grid point values \vec{X}_i in the interior. Applying the discretised field equations at the interior points and the discretised boundary conditions at the boundary points we get,

$$[K_{ib}] \cdot \vec{X}_b + [K_{ii}] \cdot \vec{X}_i = \lambda [N_{ii}] \vec{X}_i \quad (22)$$

$$[K_{bb}] \cdot \vec{X}_b + [K_{bi}] \cdot \vec{X}_i = 0 \quad (23)$$

$$\therefore \{ [K_{ii}] - [K_{ib}][K_{bb}]^{-1}[K_{bi}] - \lambda [N_{ii}] \} \vec{X}_i = 0 \quad (24)$$

and thus the buckling eigenvalue and mode shape is found.

4 Results and Model Validation

The derived model was used to simulate the buckling behaviour of a square VAT plate with unit in-plane dimensions ($l_x = l_y = 1$) under four different boundary conditions A1, A2, B1 and B2, as illustrated in Figures 2 and 3. For case A the transverse edges $y = 0$ and $y = 1$ are free to move while for case B they are constrained. For both cases A and B the applied loading was either constant $N_x = 1$ (A1 and B1) or constant $u = 0.001$ (A2 and B2) along the edges $x = 0$ and $x = 1$. Note, that since the fibre orientations may vary along the edges the boundary can deform if it is free to do so (see Figure 2). Finally, for all four cases the edges are assumed to be pinned against transverse deflection. Orthotropic carbon-epoxy material properties were defined as $E_{11} = 150\text{GPa}$, $E_{22} = 8.8\text{GPa}$, $G_{12} = 4.8\text{GPa}$, $G_{13} = G_{23} = 4\text{GPa}$ and $\nu_{12} = 0.35$. Simulations were run

on several symmetric 4-ply VAT laminates with nominal span to thickness ratios (L/t) of 100:1 and 50:1. For the 4-ply $[90 \pm \langle 0 | 70 \rangle]_s$, these aspect ratios would reduce by a factor of 3 in the areas of maximum thickness build-up, thereby increasing transverse shear effects.

Figure 2: VAT plate illustrating first set of boundary conditions A: applied unit load or end shortening with transverse edges free

Figure 3: VAT plate illustrating first set of boundary conditions B: applied unit load or end shortening with transverse edges constrained

The numerical results were verified using quadratic S8R "thick" shell elements and linear C3D8R brick elements with enhanced hourglassing control in the FEM package ABAQUS. In order to represent the VAT fibre and thickness distributions a straight fibre composite layup was de-

fined for each S8R element using the ABAQUS composite layup manager. The shell offset was then set relative to Curve 2 in Figure 1 in order to model the non-symmetric thickness variation. For the 3D model the variable thickness outline of the VAT plate was created as a solid part and then uniformly meshed using a single brick element per ply, with constant material orientation prescribed for each element depending on its location in the xyz-space. Mesh convergence studies were performed for each configuration to find the number of grid points/elements (N) required in the x- and y-directions for the DQM/FE analysis to obtain converged solutions. Thus, meshsizes of $N_{DQ} = 30 \times 30$, $N_{2D} = 50 \times 50$ and $N_{3D} = 4 \times 40 \times 40$ were used throughout the analysis.

Table 1 compares the results obtained by the present theory with the FEM solutions. The DQM ($N = 30 \times 30$) and 3D FEM ($N = 4 \times 40 \times 40$) buckling mode shapes for a $[90 \pm < 0|45 >]_s$ laminate under Case A2 boundary conditions are compared in Figures 4 and 5. The mode shapes can be seen to be very similar even though the DQ mesh is much coarser than the 3D FEM solution, thus saving computational effort.

Figure 4: DQM buckling mode shape of a $[90 \pm < 0|45 >]_s$ laminate under Case A2

Table 1 shows that the results of the present theory correlate closely with the 2D FE analysis for all configurations. This suggests that the reduced stiffness approach of modelling the coupled stretching-bending problem is accurate for the analysed buckling problem. Furthermore, the present theory shows equal accuracy to a 2D "thick" shell element with the added advantage of lower computational cost. Since pre-buckling transverse shear effects were ignored in the present theory and are incorporated in 2D FE, it can be concluded that transverse shear effects are negligible for linear fibre variations with local length to thickness ratios of up to $L/t = 35:1$. However, transverse shear effects

Figure 5: 3D FEM buckling mode shape of a $[90 \pm < 0|45 >]_s$ laminate under Case A2

may allow further spreading of loads to supported regions for non-uniform fibre variations. Therefore, the inclusion of transverse shear in the pre-buckling problem remains a topic of interest.

As shown in Table 1, the results of the present theory correlate generally well with the 3D FEM results. Most results are within 5% of the full 3D FE solution and for a number of configurations the results are within 1%. On the other hand, Table 1 clearly highlights a striking inaccuracy in some of the results especially for laminates under boundary condition B2 and the $[90 \pm < 0|45 >]_s$ laminate under A2. The results for Case B2 show that the present and 2D FE solution for the $[90 \pm < 0|45 >]_s$ laminate are up to 21% more conservative than 3D FEM. As the nominal thickness of the $[90 \pm < 0|45 >]_s$ laminate doubles from $L/t = 100$ to $L/t = 50$ the predicted results, counterintuitively, become even more conservative. One explanation for this phenomenon is that the assumption of modelling the structure as a flat non-symmetric plate is only valid up to a certain point. As the thickness build-up becomes more pronounced with higher fibre variations or the total nominal thickness of the laminate is increased, the laminate will increasingly behave more like a shell. This will naturally result in a higher buckling load than if the structure is assumed to behave as a flat plate.

Table 1 also shows that this effect has different magnitudes depending on the laminate configuration. For example the present solution for the $[0 \pm < 45|0 >]_s$ laminate under B1 is within 2% for both nominal thicknesses. Indeed Figure 6 shows that the present model accurately predicts the buckling load as the fibre angle T_1 , and therefore the thickness build-up, is increased for the laminate $[0 \pm < T_1|0 >]_s$ under boundary condition B2. Only when $T_1 = 70^\circ$, representing a local increase in thickness of 200%, do we see a significant deviation. On the other

hand, the results for a $[90 \pm < 0 | T_2 >]_s$ laminate under boundary conditions B2 in Figure 7 show a different scenario. Even for a low steering angle of $T_2 = 30$ there is a remarkable reduction in the buckling load prediction, and as T_2 is further increased, the original assumption of the VAT plate buckling as a flat plate becomes increasingly more inaccurate.

Figure 6: Comparison of DQM and 3D FEM buckling loads versus fibre angle T_1 for a $[0 \pm < T_1 | 0 >]_s$ laminate under case B1 with nominal $L/t = 100$

Figure 7: Comparison of DQM, 2D FE and 3D FEM buckling loads versus fibre angle T_2 for a $[90 \pm < 0 | T_2 >]_s$ laminate under case B2 with nominal $L/t = 100$

Thus, a VAT plate with thickness variations does indeed behave and buckle like a shell as proposed in Section 2.1 with the associated increase in buckling load. However, comparisons between the present theory and 3D FEM buckling mode shapes in Figures 4 and 5 suggest that the VAT panel still buckles in a plate mode shape and may

therefore follow a stable post buckling path. Thus it may be possible to design a panel that takes the best features of both worlds; the improved buckling performance of a shell coupled with the stable post-buckling path of a plate.

5 Conclusions

The buckling behaviour of laminates with variable fibre orientations and coupled variations in laminate thickness was investigated taking into account the effects of transverse shear deformation. The transverse shear effects were incorporated by using the well-known Hellinger-Reissner mixed variational principle [21], thus arriving at a 2D equivalent single-layer formulation. The thickness variation of the VAT laminate was modelled by assuming the laminate behaves as a flat plate with the reference surface coincident with the mid-plane of the nominal laminate thickness. The coupled stretching-bending problem of the ensuing non-symmetric laminate was approximated by solving the buckling problem of a symmetric laminate with reduced stiffness matrices. The model was solved in the strong form using the Differential Quadrature method and shown to be in good agreement with 2D FE and high fidelity 3D FE techniques with an associated reduction in computational effort required.

However, for high fibre variations with high local thickness build-up the assumption of modelling the laminate as an unsymmetric flat plate was shown to be too conservative. In some cases this effect was observed for fibre variations as low as 30° . Thus, it can be concluded that VAT panels with fibre and thickness variations as manufactured by the CTS technique behave as shells and therefore have higher buckling loads than an equivalent flat plate without the thickness variations. It is interesting to note that first observations suggest that these laminates seem to retain the stable buckling mode shapes of plates. Thus, the possibility to design a panel which couples the improved buckling performance of a shell with the stable post-buckling path of a plate is created.

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Table 1: Comparison of DQM, 2D FEM and 3D FEM buckling eigenvalues for various VAT laminates under boundary conditions A1, A2, B1 and B2. Load and displacement control eigenvalues are in N/m and mm respectively.

A1: Load control (N/m) with free transverse edges					
Laminate	L/t (nominal,thickest)	Present	FEM S8R	FEM C3D8R	Accuracy (%)
[0± < 45 0 >] _s	100, 70	2.26E+05	2.28E+05	2.25E+05	0.10
	50, 35	1.77E+06	1.79E+06	1.76E+06	0.23
[90± < 0 45 >] _s	100, 70	2.20E+05	2.31E+05	2.22E+05	-0.75
	50, 35	1.70E+06	1.80E+06	1.71E+06	-0.47
A2: Displacement control (mm) with free transverse edges					
Laminate	L/t (nominal,thickest)	Present	FEM S8R	FEM C3D8R	Accuracy (%)
[0± < 45 0 >] _s	100, 70	1.80E+05	1.82E+05	1.82E+05	-0.65
	50, 35	1.41E+06	1.43E+06	1.43E+06	-0.74
[90± < 0 45 >] _s	100, 70	1.28E+05	1.31E+05	1.37E+05	-7.34
	50, 35	9.98E+05	1.03E+06	1.08E+06	-7.74
B1: Load control (N/m) with constrained transverse edges					
Laminate	L/t (nominal,thickest)	Present	FEM S8R	FEM C3D8R	Accuracy (%)
[0± < 45 0 >] _s	100, 70	0.188	0.180	0.185	1.55
	50, 35	0.735	0.710	0.747	-1.53
[90± < 0 45 >] _s	100, 70	1.045	1.050	1.018	2.55
	50, 35	4.036	4.100	3.863	4.27
B2: Displacement control (mm) with constrained transverse edges					
Laminate	L/t (nominal,thickest)	Present	FEM S8R	FEM C3D8R	Accuracy (%)
[0± < 45 0 >] _s	100, 70	0.091	0.090	0.092	-1.53
	50, 35	0.356	0.354	0.391	-9.58
[90± < 0 45 >] _s	100, 70	0.370	0.359	0.406	-9.72
	50, 35	1.445	1.409	1.744	-20.63

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